

ISic1266

I.Sicily inscription 1266

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140755

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (α) τ (αχθονίοις).
2. Χαίρο[υ]σα αἰ-
3. εἰ γλυκυτάτη
4. ζήσασα ἔτη [—]
5. πατήρ τ [ῆ] ἰδίᾳ]
6. [θυ]γατρ[ὶ ἐποίησεν].
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492873

EDCS 39101635

PHI 140755

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

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